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The Use of Genre Based Approach in Training and Mentoring for Improving Argument Skills in Research Articles Journal Writing for Social and Humanity Authors

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Abstract

Argumentation in writing research articles is very crucial for showing the position of authors in a certain science field, but the social and humanity authors are still lower in skill for argumentation. This research investigated the using and impact of the Genre Based Approach (GBA) in training and mentoring of Research Article writing in improving the skill of argumentation in writing RA. The aim of this study is to describe the activity of learning and teaching by using GBA in training and mentoring of writing RA for social and humanity authors and the impact of this training and mentoring on the skill of argumentation in RAs writing. The material and steps of learning and teaching activity are adapted and modified from Widodo (2006) who stated that the rule of GBA is to prepare, focus, task, evaluate and elaborate. Moreover, Ferris & Hedgcock (2005) also explained that GBA is started from joint construction and independent construction stages when students start to write. The instruments of this research were direct observation and RAs draft analysis. Direct observing is also conducted to record every side of GBA design for teaching writing articles. To find the effect of GBA in training and mentoring to improve argumentative skills, the content analysis to the draft of RAs is conducted. The Result shows that the first the activity of training and mentoring writing RAs by using GBA to improve argumentation skills can be described from prepare, focus, task, evaluate and elaborate. The second finding shows that the participants have competence in writing argumentative for each section of RAS. Thus, it can be concluded that GBA in training and mentoring to write RAs is effective to improve argumentative skills in writing class especially writing RAs class.

Keywords: Genre Based Approach (GBA) Design, Argumentative Writing Skill, Research Article

1. Introduction

According to Arsyad (2018) writing is an effective way to educate the community massively to improve the standard of living into a better life. Firdaus (2018) also said that by writing scientific articles and disseminating them to citizens, a nation will achieve rapid and equitable progress. It is understood that by accessing the latest and greatest research results, people will be provoked to study, try, believe, use and make it a new better habit.

Although the competence of writing is crucial in the development of science and technology and must be the thing that has been mastered by lecturers, but the fact is that the competence of writing is still low in Indonesian academics with indicators of the low number of publications of research journal articles from Indonesia. The knowledge, skills, motivation and mindset are factors in the low quantity and quality of scientific publications of Indonesian academics. The development of technology requires a variety of scientific discoveries needed by the people's lives must be shared to various parts of the world both orally, especially with published scientific writing. Steven R. Covey (BPSDM-Kemendikbud, 2012) mentioned that scientific publication activities are one form of effort to renew the mental. Arsyad (2018) said that scientific publications are important for the development and dissemination of science that is awaited and needed by the community.

The data also showed that Indonesian academic publications are mostly in the fields of design, technology, health and medicine such as: Engineering (15.14%), Medicine (10.64%), Computer Science (10.2%), Agriculture and Biological Sciences (9.57%), Physics and Astronomy (5.39%), while publications in the field of Social Sciences only (4.74%) arts and humanities only (0.91%) (Kemenristekdikti, 2016:18). This data shows that very few Indonesian academics in the field of social sciences and humanities have successfully published in reputable international journals. Conditions in Bengkulu Province such as at the University of Bengkulu are not much different; in the last three years (2014, 2015 and 2016) from 740 lecturers from the University of Bengkulu there were only 51 publications of lecturers in reputable international journals, mostly produced by lecturers in the field of Design and Technology (Form AIPT Universitas Bengkulu, 2016).

Data that shows low quantity and also shows the personal quality of lecturers in the field of social and humanities (Arts and Humanities) which only shows a figure of 0.91%, becomes a motivation to research more about problems or obstacles experienced, especially lecturers in the field of science. Some previous research such as that conducted by Arsyad (2019) which gave a questionnaire to lecturers of social sciences and humanities about the perception against writing Research Journal Articles to be published in international journals or reputable journals that found that the problems found are the problem of knowledge and skills. The lack of knowledge and skills makes AJP writers from the social sciences and humanities unable to compete.

From this, it can be known that the issue of competence owned by lecturers of social sciences and humanities in writing AJP in accordance with standard AJP is one of the problems that encourage low publication. Arsyad (2018) also found that the low competence of English-speaking groups of lecturers of social sciences and humanities became a factor inhibiting the group's lecturers from accessing international journals both journal information and as a reference in writing AJP. These factors are what the solution wants to find so that the consolidation of low complement of lecturers in the field of social sciences and humanities can be minimized and in the end there is an increase in active participation of authors of social sciences and humanities in writing AJP published in reputable journals.

According to Arsyad (2018), one cause of poor quality of the academics Indonesia does not yet understand the style of rhetoric and subsection standard every part of the journal articles research in English as described by (swales, 1990 and 2004) and differences and similarities style rhetoric scientific article in Indonesian language and English. Some research that found the problems lack of understanding the author of the journal articles research from Indonesia as discovered by Safnil (2001), Mirahayuni (2002), Adnan (2009), Arsyad and Wardhana (2014), Arsyad and Arono (2015) and Arsyad and Arono (2016). From this problem can be described that this conclusion needs an approach to training and coaching in writing RA which is effective and efficient to increase knowledge and skill in writing argumentative.

As an offer of a solution to change perceptions negative about writing RA, increase the motivation, competence, and skill in writing RA knowledge was too simple training and worked effectively and efficiently. This must be considered, activities time and the saturation lecturers participants a class training writing. One approach learning writing (writing) offered and updated is learning based genre (genre based approach) cut down with GBA. GBA approach was chosen because the work calls learners to focus on what will be written and who will read his writings. This method is suitable for training RA writing. As according to Hyland (2000), the use of a genre-based approach in the learning of scientific writing is the most suitable approach because writing and

teaching writing is social communication activities as people do in real life and genre-based writing learning theory does this. L Trong (2011) said "most of the students gained the control over the key features of the required recount genre in terms of social purposes, language features and schematic structure. The necessity and usefulness of the application of the teaching-learning cycle into learning the recount genre were predominantly recognized among students.

Various researches on the application of Genre Based Approach have been conducted in writing classes as research by Rashidi & Mazdayazna (2016); Atai & Shoja (2011); Dirgeyasa (2016); and Elashri (2013), but research on the application of GBA to lecturers in writing Research Journal Articles for international publications have never been conducted.

From the background above, it can be stated that it is important to be researched on the use of training and mentoring approaches to write research journal articles using the Genre Based Approach abbreviated as GBA in an effort to increase motivation, improve the skill of argumentative in writing RAs. Furthermore, the problem formulation can be prepared: 1) How is the implementation of GBA in mentoring write AJP to improve the argumentative skills of writers in the field of social sciences and humanities; 2. How is the quality of argumentation of author in writing the abstract of RAs after getting training and mentoring by using genre-based approach based as recommended by Yang (2016)? 3. How is the quality of argumentation of author in writing introduction of RAs after getting training and mentoring by using genre-based approach based as recommended by Yang (2016) 4. How is the quality of argumentation of author in writing result and discussion of RAs after getting training and mentoring by using a genre-based approach based as recommended by Yang (2016)

2. Literature Review

2.1. GBA in training and mentoring RA writing

Training and coaching wrote the study by the journal articles based approach considering the importance of science writing and publicity for the development of science, then need to design / design learning wrote (writing) discourse that can effectively increase the motivation, knowledge and skill in writing academics in the field of social and the humanities. One of the approaches recommended can work effectively is the approach based (GBA). GBA in writing scientific work is ever more popular because this approach proved to be the most efficient in particular international to train students to learn in a country users English (Dudley-Evans, 1997). According to Widodo (2006), a genre based approach is defined as: teaching learners how to make use of language patterns to achieve a coherent and purposefully composition (p: 173). Widodo (2006) explained that the genre of the theory-based approach developed systemic functional grammar in which a language and functions. be correlated So, according to Widodo, in this approach is a professor or instructors have to explain and show a student or trainee three important aspect of a text, scientific namely: purpose organization and the reader and after that train them wrote the text very well based on the purpose of, organization and certain readers.

In learning based genre of learning and there is five-step; preparation, concerned with the purpose of learning, focus exercise assignment task, evaluation and elaboration. Some advantages of using an approach based particularly in the context of the learning of languages the genre of foreign such as: 1) this approach is focused on the process of writing in which students are aware of what makes a writing is good and how to achieve it in terms of the content and organization; 2) approach encourages faculty and students practice of composing type particular text together between faculty and students and teachers could transfer knowledge and experience writing them; and directly to students; 3) by adopting this students trained to consider three important aspects of a writing (purpose, the rhetoric and readers) in writing a kind of scientific text (Widodo, 2006). Thus, academics in the field of social and the humanities are driven to think about why they should write the text certain, how organization text that is Ideal to a kind of the text and who will read the text.

2.2. Writing on the international journal reputable Skill based on competence in writing RA for international journal

In research and publication of reputable international journal, Jeong in Han (2008) stressed on some aspects of skills such as; 1) Originality and novelty to the research and publication written; 2. fit and strong planning and design research; and 3. making publication as a tool of storytelling for the best quality of knowledge.

This shows that skill which has been had as author for research article (RA) for reputable journal include reading skill for knowledge and its scoop to find the novelty which is guaranteed improvement of knowledge and community better life quality.

Secondly, having the skill to arrange design that can make belief from others authors or researchers about validity, reliability dan accountability of research. thirdly, having the skill to present research findings which can make sure from content, rhetorical and argument of presented RA.

In this research, the focus of skill to be improved: the first, knowledge of writing RA based on international journal standard and strategy to write argumentative RA in each part of RA such as argument in abstract, argument is introduction, argument in method and argument in result and discussion RA section.

Some previous research related to the study such as Arsyad (2001), Adnan (2009), Arsyad (2013.a), Arsyad (2013.b), Arsyad & Wardhana (2014) and Arsyad & Arono (2016). The objective of the researches is to find out how the rhetorical style, citation style and linguistic features are used by Indonesian authors in writing RA in other knowledge disciplines compared with other texts in the same kind of text. Then, to find out about the similarity and deferences of RA rhetorical style in Indonesian and English.

Based on his research, Arsyad (2001) suggested a more suitable rhetorical model of writing RA for accommodate communicative unit in Indonesian RA introduction in social and humanity which is a revision from rhetorical model in introduction section of RA in English by Swalles (1990) called by CARS (creating a research space). It is different with CARS, PJP model has four moves and each move has more steps compared with the move and step in CARS model. According to Arsyad (2003), PJP can accommodate more various communicative units in RA introduction section than CARS model from Swalles (1990).

Adnan (2009) had analysed the rhetorical structure of RA introduction in education knowledge discipline which is written by Indonesian authors by using CARS model from Swalles as a parameter. He found that from 20 RA introductions by Indonesia language in his research corpus, no one of them was suitable with rhetorical style in RA introduction in English as Swalles (1990) found.

The main difference according to Adnan is in move 1 (establishing a territory) where the majority of authors in Indonesia RA discuss the main point and its usefulness of their research by focusing on practical problems which occurred to common people or government not relevant discourse community. Besides of that, no one of the authors of RA from Indonesia related their research based niche from relevant previous research finding as in the move 2 models or in establishing a niche section (Swales. 1990). Adnan suggests an ideal problem solution (IPS) which is modification from CARS model for getting introduction rhetorical in Indonesian moreover in education knowledge discipline.

Moreover, research finding from Arsyad & Wardhana (2014) and Arsyad & Arono (2015) focus more on rhetorical analysis type and linguistics future in the introduction section of Indonesian RA in the social and humanity field. Their researches show that there are differences between Indonesian and English rhetorical in the introduction section. Arsyad & Arono concluded that the differences between Indonesian and English authors in the introduction section of RA such as: 1) Indonesian author of RA considers that preparing readers to read the RA is very important; 2) Indonesian author of RA considers to support the important topic or title of the research by personal reason and based on previous researches; 3) Indonesian author of RA tends to support their research by subjective and personal reasons. From the research, it can be described that Indonesian authors need to

change mindset and style in writing RA in international standard. By this condition, their RAs can publish in international journals.

2.3. Argumentation quality in writing Research Articles (RAs)

The first, in presenting argumentative writing on abstract in RA, the author can choose some types of argumentative style such as Appeal to problemacy, Appeal to salience, Appeal to topicality, Appeal to Magnitude (Yang, 2016). Correct and strong argumentative choice in the abstract section of RA shows the skill of the author. It also can give positive motivation to the readers to make deeper in reading the RAs presented. The quality of presenting argumentative in RAs becomes the focus of this research by implementing GBA.

Secondly, in the introduction of RA according to Yang (2016), the author usually presents argumentation for their RA by showing the mistakes from previous research, showing the weakness of previous research, showing the limited scope of previous research, or by showing that there is no the same to previous research or new problem for all previous research. The acuration of choice for the type of argumentative in RA introduction shows the skill of the author in writing RA and publication of RA journal. Arsyad (2018) said that an author and researcher must understand the scoop of science and information fully she or he writes and will be published so she or he can follow the development of information from the science scoop she or he studies and will be published.

The third, in the method section the author usually strengthens his or her arguments by saying the methods which are used by famous researchers or many researchers (Yang, 2016). in this part or section, the author must be focused to share that he or she focused on the research subject and can give guarantee that the research is valid and no doubt in its process, analysis and concluding. This skill will be a parameter of author quality in writing RA and publishing it.

Fourth, author argumentation in result and discussion in RA, according to Yang (2016), can be done as stating similarity or supporting previous researches, contrasting argument to the previous researches, and stating continuing previous researches. This skill will be the parameter of author quality in writing RA and publishing it.

3. Methods

3.1. Participant

This study used mix method. According to Gay, using descriptive research qualitative is used to test hypotheses or to answer questions related to the status of the research subject (Best. WJ, 1977). Then, for quantitative research, follow Cresswell, J.W (2012) to find the perception of participants after implementing of GBA. It is predicted that GBA is effective to be used in teaching writing, so this is needed to be described how the real implementation is. For answering the research question, 36 lecturers from some universities in Bengkulu were invited to follow a training and mentoring writing RAs by using GBA.

3.2. Instrument

A training and mentoring in research article writing classes for international journal publication are conducted to implement the GBA to get its strengthen. As Widodo (2006) said that the rule of GBA, prepare, focus, task, evaluate and elaborate. Ferris & Hedgcock's (2005) GBA was specifically on joint construction and independent construction stages when students start to write. RAs drafts from participants are also taken as data of the research to know the impact of innovative GBA implementation toward the competency of argumentative in writing RAs.

3.3. Data Analysis procedures

The data of implementation innovative GBA in RA writing class is analysed by trimming and displaying from preparation, main activity and evaluation. Then, the data of the impact of innovative GBA toward participants are analyzed by using Paired two tailed test with SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science). For data of participants RAs draft after following this GBA class is analysed by content analysis based on the type of argumentation for each move and steps of RAs as recommended by Yang (2016).

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1. Finding

4.1.1. The implementation of GBA to improve argumentative skill in writing RA

The activity of training and mentoring writing RAs by using GBA to improve argumentative skills can be described from prepare, focus, task, evaluate and elaborate.

Table 1. Lesson plan of GBA design in RAs writing class

Learning Activity	Focus	Target	Lesson Material
Preparing: Opening and Orientation of Learning	Motivation & Building Self-awareness as academician or lecturers related to Nation & community	Preparing fresh authors to build up themselves to be a good authors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Data of research publication in Indonesia and compared with other countries. ✓ The government policy about publication. ✓ The impact of publications on social life.
Main activity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Focusing: Giving concepts, form, principles, and strategies for writing RA. ✓ Modeling and Discussing each item of RA ✓ Practicing to write RA based the model is given. 	Focusing on the goal of Learning how to write RAs	Understanding the Goal of writing RA and implementing to each part of RA (sections, Moves and steps)	Kind of RAs RA rhetorical and its sections, moves and steps. How to write argumentative and persuasive text to strength RAs.
Evaluation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Giving the task to independently writing part of RAs Revising incomplete or not suitable parts of RAs Helping to send RAs draft to international Journal 	Author independent and self-confident in writing RAs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Trained RAs author ✓ Continuing elaboration of writing RAs activities. 	How to struggle in publishing our RAs to International Journal. The history of famous authors from rejecting to other accepting journal.

From table 1 above, it can be seen that in teaching and learning writing RAs by using GBA has three core of learning and teaching activities, they were the first, preparing with opening and Orientation of Learning; the second was main activity with giving concepts, form, principles, and strategies for writing RA, discussing each item of RA, Practicing to write RA based the model is given; the third was evaluation with activities such as

giving the task to independently writing part of RAs, revising incomplete or not suitable part of RAs and helping to send RAs draft to international Journal

4.1.2. The skill of writing argumentation in the abstract section of RA

After analysing the draft of RAs from the social and humanity author, it can be presented as in the table below:

Table 2: Argumentation style of social and humanity authors after following GBA writing class

NO	Argumentation type in Abstract	Frequency	Percentage
1	Appeal to problemacity	21	58%
2	Appeal to salience	6	17%
3	Appeal to topicality	5	14%
4	Appeal to Magnitude	4	11%
Total		36	100%

From table 2 above, it can be seen that type of argumentation from social and humanity author such as appeal to problemacity 21 (58%), appeal to salience 6 (20%). for appeal to topicality is 5 (14%). The last, for appeal to magnitude is 4 (11%).

More than a half of them write an argument in abstract by saying problem such as in RA extract below:

Extract 1:

(S-1) Group counseling as a guidance and counseling service does not have a standard instrument yet in assessing its activities. (S-2) This study was designed to develop a group counseling assessment instrument. (S-3) Specifically, this study conducted content validity, empirical validity, and internal reliability of group counseling assessment instruments.

From the sample of abstract which is used argumentation appeal to salience problemacity type above, it can be seen that the author able to show that this work is important to be read because there is a serious problem must be solved by findings in her or his work. The author gave argumentation that there is no a strong guidance with the best standard in conducting counseling, the work in the RA tries to present the model of counseling assessment instrument.

The other participant also used appeal to salience to make strong their RA abstract. By this type of argumentation in writing RA abstract, they try to provoke the readers to read their RA because it is important to be known. It is such as in the extract of the abstract below :

Extract 2:

(S-1) The phenomena of bullying at schools have occurred very often. (S-2) Although there have been many studies conducted, those studies have not yet been well-balanced compared to the continuous presence of various bullying cases at schools from time to time up to the present.

From extract 2 above, it can be seen that the author tried to make strong his abstract by showing salience. The author wrote that the study on willingness to communicate on low willingness to communicate focusing factors on learners with high English ability is needed.

The others author also choose argumentation by appealing to topicality where they try to persuade the readers by statement that the works in important and up to date issue. The argument from the author by appealing to topicality as example in extract below:

Extract 3:

(S-1) English Learning and Teaching (ELT) in Vocational School has crucial function to help students for competition in working on the competition in international scoop. (S-2) So many people in vocational field try to find the best result of research in teaching for vocational school students.

From extract 3 above, it can be seen that after training and mentoring the author can apply to write argumentation in their RAs by appealing to topicality. It is written that study about ELT in vocational school is hot topic. Many researchers conducted this study to find the best way of ELT in vocational school, such as in a sentence

Appealing to magnitude is also used by authors to make a strong position for their abstract, for more data it can be seen to the extract of RA from the author as follow :

Extract 4:

(S-1) Mathematics is a compulsory subject in all of Indonesian high school. Problem solving ability is a competency that must be possessed in learning mathematics.

From the abstract in extract 4 above, it can be seen that the author makes a stronger position of the abstract by saying that the topic of his or her work is being discussed by people in the world. Thus, this work is important to be read.

4.1.3. Argumentation in Introduction of RA section

After following the training and mentoring the author from social and humanity field show the quality of argumentative in writing section of introduction in RA. It is more argumentative in introduction's move and steps. The argument is more clear in move 2 or in part of establishing a niche in RA's introduction. The authors show their competence in argumentation by showing the mistakes from previous research, the weakness of previous research, the limited scope of previous research, or by showing that there is no the same to previous research or new problem for all previous research.

By content analysis toward the RAs draft from the authors, the type of argumentation for each part of introduction which is used by authors can be identified as table 3 below:

Table 3: Author argumentation in RA Introduction section after following RA writing training and mentoring

NO	Argumentation style in Introduction	Frequency	Percentage
1	showing that there is no the same to previous research or new problem for all previous research.	18	50%
2	Showing the weakness of previous research	11	31%
3	Showing the limited scoop of previous research	7	19%
4	Showing the mistakes from previous research	0	0%
Total		36	100%

From table 3 above, it can be seen that the author can write argumentation for their introduction of RAs by showing unique research or no same research before is 18 (50%); Showing weakness in previous research is 11 (31%); then for 7 (19%) is showing the lack of previous research; Showing mistake for previous research is 0%. from this finding, it can be resumed that stating unique research topic I dominant used by the authors. It can be seen clearly ss example below:

Extract 5:

- (S-1) Looking at a number of the research results as presented above, there has not been explicitly found how the roles of family and religious teachings can significantly prevent bullying at schools.
- (S-2) Although there is a study undertaken by Calik, et al. (2018) vis-a-vis the need of parental role, this study has not yet explicitly accounted for what parents must do in preventing bullying at schools.

From example of the introduction in extract 5 above, it can be seen that authors' argument in introduction by showing there is no similarity with the previous research. The argumentation can be seen in sentence (S-1) which explains that there are no researches as the authors present in the RA. The author can build trust from readers by making sure that although there are many researches about bullying but preventive effort for it is not clear. This argumentation such as is in second sentences (S-2)

The other style of making argumentation is by stating weaknesses from previous research as extract 6 below:

Extract 6:

- (S-1) Although there is a study undertaken by Calik, et al. (2018) vis-a-vis the need of parental role, this study has not yet explicitly accounted for what parents must do in preventing bullying at schools.

In extract 6 above, it is seen the way of the author to present previous researches in sentence 1 (S1) and the author try to evaluate by showing weakness of the research in same sentence. The author makes stronger his or her RA by presenting the weaknesses previous researches compared with the present research.

Argumentation by showing lack or limited scoop of previous research is also used by authors after following the training and mentoring. The way of presenting showing lack or limited scoop as sample below:

Extract 7:

- (S-1) However, not many studies have been conducted on writing the method section of research articles in English, in particular the study related to students' difficulties in writing the method section.
- (S-2) Most studies deals with the structure of the method section (Lim, 2006; Bruce, 2008; Peacock, 2011; Kafes, 2016; Pramoolsook, Li and Wang, 2015; Zang and Wanaruk, 2016).
- (S-3) In addition, some studies deal with the use of themes and grammatical subjects in the method section of research articles (Martinez, 2003; Ebrahimi, 2016; Ebrahimi and Heng, 2018).
- (S-4) Inadequate attention to the method section may due to the misunderstanding that writing up this section is often considered as an easy and straightforward activity/task (Pramoolsook, Li and Wang, 2015).
- (S-5) To address the gap in previous research, we conducted a study to investigate the difficulties of ELT undergraduate students in writing the method section of research articles in English.

Example in extract 7 above shows that author presents the argument by presenting lack of information in the field of his or her research. The argument such as in sentence 1 (S-1) that not many studies have been conducted on writing the method section of research articles in English, in particular the study related to students' difficulties in writing the method section. In sentences 2 to sentence 4 (S-2 to S-4) the author also presents some researches result with their weakness and the author claimed that the researches needed to be add from data or information or they are needed more continue researches. Then in sentence 5 (S-5) the author shows that his research is very important to fulfill the gap from previous researches.

4.1.4. The quality of argumentation in writing Result and Discussion

Argumentation for presenting in RA result and discussion part. The analysis as table below:

Table 4. The style of argumentative from the author in result and discussion after following training and mentoring by GBA

NO	Authors Argumentation type in Result & Discussion	Frequency	Percentage
1	stating similarity or supporting previous researches	20	56%
2	contrasting arguments	10	28%
3	stating continuing previous researches	6	17%
Total		36	100%

From table above it can be described that the argumentation quality of author after following training and mentoring in part result and discussion satiating similarity or supporting previous researches is 20 authors (56%). Argumentation by contrasting arguments as much as 10 (28%). then argumentation by stating continuing previous researches is 6 (17%). Similarity or supporting strategy is dominant as example below:

Extract 8:

(S-1) The findings of this study are in line with the studies conducted by Erdogdu (2016) and Yanez, et.al. (2018). (S-2) However, both Erdogdu and Yanez still place the role of parents or family in terms of children's bullying prevention in a small portion. (S-3) In their studies, family or parents do have a contribution in preventing children from bullying at schools, but their role is considered not yet dominant. (S-4) The findings of this study reaffirm that family or parents are the main pillars in preventing children from bullying at schools.

From extract 8 of the result and discussion section above, it can be described that the author makes stronger the RA by stating similarities or supporting previous research. The author stated that his research has similarities with research findings from Erdogdu (2016) and Yanez, et.al. (2018). The statement can be found in sentence 1 (S-1). The author also explains that his research emphasizes completing previous research as in sentences 1 to 4 (S-2 to S-4).

The others author about 20% choose making argumentation by stating contrasting and stating that their researches are different with the previous study. This style is by contrasting. This can be seen in the following example:

Extract 9:

[P-1] Introduction of solar lighting units in rural communities has helped children to study even after dark. More than 50,000 children in India are attending Barefoot Night Schools after sunset (as they work at home and herd livestock during the day). The very belief that educational qualification is not a barrier for picking up practical skills, and serving communities makes

[P-2] The illiterate men and women irrespective of their age are being trained to work as school teachers, doctors, midwives, dentists, health workers, solar engineers, water drillers, hand pump mechanics, architects, artisans, designers, masons, communicators, water testers, phone operators, blacksmiths, carpenters, computer instructors and accountants.

[P-3] As of May 2010, 480 people have been trained as Barefoot Solar Engineers (BSEs), of whom 230 are women. These BSEs have fabricated, installed, repaired and maintained nearly 16,000 fixed solar units and 9,762 solar lanterns across 16 states of India and 20 of the least developed countries like Afghanistan, Bhutan, Kenya and Cameroon

Example of RA result or finding in extract 9 shows that the author makes strong the position of result and discussion of his RA by contrasting to previous study as in sentences (P-1 to P-3]. the author presents something new which is not researched before or it is missed from previous discussion. 17% author after following the training and mentoring by using GBA shows the quality of argument by continuing previous researches. It can be seen in extract 10 below:

Extract 10:

[P-1] That this research was carried out to provide assistance in learning whether the challenges carried out by students in working on the test questions on the questions given, in the opinion of Chaudrey (1990), time is an important element, a reader needs time in the discussion of ideas. It is time to move on, and revisions must be part of the process. Regarding the deadline and performance of examinees, Elliot and Marquart (2004) have conducted research. The aim of their study was to examine the effect of extended time during testing on the performance.

[P-2] Inspired by Elliot and Marquart, this research was conducted. This research, carried out at Kaur 03 High School, used 2 different classes randomly selected from class 11. The class taken as research material was 11th grade which will be the subject of this study. They were asked to read types of narrative text readings based on certain topics. Under various test conditions, the standard time limit (90 minutes) and also under the extended time limit (120 minutes).

From example of argument from author after following training and mentoring on part of result or finding above, the author present the argument by showing similarity or continuing previous research in paragraph 2 [P-2] and related to some previous researches such is paragraph 1 [P-1]. The author stated that her research is inspired by previous research which was done by Elliot and Maquat (2004).

4.2. Discussion

4.2.1. Implementation GBA in training and mentoring to RA writing class

The first, the steps of implementation genre Based Approach (GBA) in training and mentoring class for writing Research Articles (RAs) in this research are planning, practicing and evaluating of class activity. In planning activity GBA provided such as; 1) preparing with opening and Orientation of Learning; 2) giving concepts, form, principles, and strategies for writing RA, discussing each item of RA, Practicing to write RA based the model is given; 3) evaluating with activities such as giving task to independently writing part of RAs, revising incomplete or not suitable part of RAs and helping to send RAs draft to international Journal. The finding is in line with the concept of GBA implantation from Widodo (2006) said that the rule of GBA is to prepare, focus, task, evaluate and elaborate. Then, Hyland (2000); Almacioglu, et al (2018) and Arono & Safnil (2019) also said that GBA was specifically on joint construction and independent construction stages when students start to write.

Secondly, in practicing of learning and teaching writing RAs by using genre based approach it starting from explaining concepts and focusing on the goal of writing RAs, then discussing part of RAs consisting of moves and steps, and then practicing to write RAs together and revising the RAs. These steps are in line with Widodo (2006); Hyland (2000); Batubara (2013); Mazdayazna & Rashidi (2016); and Cartens, A (2009) that they concluded for steps of genre based approach starting from giving concept (focus), example (modelling), ways (trying) and practice it (together and independently).

Thirdly, to evaluate the achievement of students or participants the instructor or teacher use the standard of RAs rhetorical from (Swalles, 2009). The evaluation to products of GBA training or teaching based, the teacher looked to the moves and steps of RAs such as abstract, introduction, methods, result and discussion, and conclusion and recommendation with all of their steps. This way of evaluation is in line with Adnan, Z. (2014); Swales & Feak (2009); Ariyansfar, et all (2020); Changpueng, P (2013) and Safnil (2018) they discussed that evaluation of writing text must back to the rhetorical of the text.

4.2.2. Author Argumentation skill in writing Research Article (RA) abstract

The finding of the research shows that in inviting the readers, the author has strategy to provoke the readers in order to read the RA. Each section of the RA has different ways. Yang (2016) said that in writing argumentative abstract, there are four style such as; appeal to salience, appeal to magnitude, appeal to topicality and appeal to problemacity. The position of the argumentation for abstract is in move 1 or it is called introduction.

The using GBA in training and mentoring to write RA is effective in improving skill of writing RA to be published in international journals. Argumentation in abstract is very crucial because by finding abstract, the reader will decide to continue for reading or leave the RA (Arsyad, 2019). More over. Arsyad (2019) stated that it is right that the type of RA text is more argumentative although Indonesian authors tend to leave from debating and arguing. It is same with Van Maanen (1989) that for building trust for others in writing for him, "*We try to persuade others by 'presenting a coherent point of view told with grace, wit, and felicity.'*"

The skill of authors after following the training and mentoring to write RA argumentatively in abstract is appeal to problemacy is 21%, appeal to salience is 17%, appeal to topicality is 14%, and appeal to magnitude is 11%. Thus, appeal to problemacy is dominant style to make strong RA abstract. This finding is supported the previous study from Yang (2016).

From the discussion above, it can be resumed that the skill of making argumentation in abstract is very important to make sure that the RA can be suitable to be published in journal international.

4.2.3. Author argumentation skill in RA introduction section

In introduction, the author presents his or her skill of argumentation by showing the mistakes from previous research, the weakness of previous research, the limited scope of previous research, or showing that there is no the same to previous research or new problem for all previous research. This finding is supported previous researches from Rashidi & Mazdayazna (2016) which had found that by using GBA learning of writing activity can improve needed aspects for best quality of writing. The quality of argumentative introduction from author in training and mentoring as suggested by Yang (2016).

4.2.4. Author Argumentation skill in RA finding and discussion section

The authors after following training and mentoring had skill to make argumentation in finding and research such as stating similarity or supporting previous researches; Argumentation by contrasting arguments; and argumentation by stating continuing previous researches. Dominant from them is giving argument by presenting similarity or supporting strategy. The research finding is in line with (Widodo, 2006; Pudji A, 2013) they concluded that by GBA is suitable method in writing class. In line with Hyland (2003); Rose, D & Marthin (2012); Samsudin Z & Arif (2018) and Wardhana (2020)

Arsyad (2019) also say that in writing RAs international must be argumentative so can show the novelty for the knowledge development. Argumentation skill from the author in this research is clear and the author have changed their style in writing RA from shopping list without critics and correction to the previous researches to the critics and debating to the other authors. This is as study from Adnan (2014), he found that Indonesian authors do not want to show critics and debate to the other authors because according to them, it can caused bad relation among the authors.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1. Conclusion

The first, in GBA implementation for RA writing training and mentoring to improve argumentative skill is conducted by steps; focusing to write RA argumentatively, modelling in section and move argumentation type and style, practicing write together and practicing individually in giving argumentation to all of RAs section and moves.

Secondly, the skill of writing abstract of RA after following the training and mentoring can be reported as appeal to problemacy is 21%, appeal to salience is 17%, appeal to topicality is 14%, and appeal to magnitude is 11%. Thus, appeal to problemacy is dominant style to make strong RA abstract. It can be stated that GBA is effective to share the argumentative skill in writing RA to social and humanity authors.

The third, the skill of writing introduction of RA after following the training and mentoring can be concluded as follow: showing unique work (no the same to previous research or new problem in research is 50%, showing the weakness from previous researches 31%, showing the limited scoop from previous researches is 19%, showing the mistakes from previous researches is 0%. Thus, argument in introduction by type showing unique work (no the same to previous research or new problem in research is dominant style to make strong RA introduction. Then, no author or researcher of social and humanity in this study brave to choose showing the mistakes from previous researches in making argumentation for their introduction of RA. So, It can be stated that GBA is effective to share the argumentative skill in writing RA to social and humanity authors.

Fourth, the skill of writing finding and discussion of RA after following the training and mentoring can be concluded as follow: stating similarity or supporting previous researches is 56%; contrasting argument to previous researches is 28%; stating to continue previous researches is 17%. So, in this research, the type of argumentation with stating similarity or supporting previous researches is dominantly used by the authors. Then, the stressing point of the research that GBA is effective to share the argumentative skill in writing RA to social and humanity authors.

5.2. Recommendation

The first, for the authors who want to upgrade the competence of writing RA can take this research finding as references especially about argumentation for each move and steps of RA. Secondly, for teachers and lecturers or instructors of training for writing classes can choose GBA as method to make focused, simple and applicable learning and teaching for writing especially writing RA. Thirdly, for university, college or school can choose and invite the lecturers and teachers to implement GBA method in improving skill of writing for students.

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